

Frameworks for Coordinated Operation to Manage Congestion and Extend the Lifespan of Distribution Networks

Hugo Andreu Oliver
Josh Eichman
Ali Agga
Energy Systems Analytics Group
Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC)
Sant Adrià del Besòs, Barcelona, Spain
{handreu, jeichman, aagga}@irec.cat

Albert Solà Vilalta
Grup d'Optimització Numèrica i Modelització
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC)
Barcelona, Spain
albert.sola.vilalta@upc.edu

Abstract—As the European Union (EU) accelerates the transition toward decentralized energy systems, users equipped with Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) are increasingly forming communities and local markets. While this integration promises economic and social gains, it also raises a critical question: can distribution networks sustain this new level of activity without causing congestion or impacting cost and performance? This study explores how different user coordination schemes shape the onset and management of congestion within distribution grids. Two approaches are examined: uncoordinated users and a Local Flexibility Market (LFM) based on reserve bids. For the latter, a two-stage stochastic model captures demand uncertainty and its effect on network operation. Findings reveal that ignoring grid constraints increases infrastructure loading, whereas congestion-aware coordination can extend network lifetime through improved loading management with minimal additional cost. Moreover, introducing reserve market participation adds operational realism, moderating battery use and acknowledging grid reliability under varying demand conditions.

Index Terms—User Coordination, Local Energy Market, Local Flexibility Market, Congestion Management, Stochastic Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

The EU has steadily strengthened its renewable energy targets, reflecting a firm and growing dedication to achieving climate neutrality and accelerating the transition toward clean energy. In parallel, recent years have seen a notable global expansion in the deployment of DERs [1], [2], [3]. Alongside this, the EU continues to advance its internal energy market by improving network interconnections and coordination, while encouraging the active involvement of individual consumers through the promotion of Energy Communities [1].

However, the fast-paced growth of renewable generation and its integration into existing grids can sometimes compromise system reliability and operational stability [4]. At the same

time, electricity demand continues to rise, fueled by population growth, urban development, and the widespread electrification of transport, heating, and industry. For example, global electricity consumption increased by 4.3% in 2024, compared with 2.5% in 2023 [5]. As access to electricity and modern technologies expands, the overall demand for energy keeps intensifying.

Traditionally, managing network congestion has depended on reinforcing grid infrastructure, which is a costly solution involving new transmission and distribution assets, transformers, and related equipment. More recently, attention has shifted toward decentralized and cost-efficient alternatives. Among these, Local Energy Markets (LEMs) have emerged as a promising tool to mitigate congestion by coordinating the flexible operation of distributed energy resources at the local level. The implementation of LEMs aims to create a more sustainable, reliable, and participatory energy system that benefits all actors involved [6], [7].

LEMs prioritize the coordination of local production and consumption [8], aiming to address key challenges in current electricity markets by taking the local context into account [9]. According to [10], a LEM can be understood as “as a market, a physical or virtual space, in which the transactions between the actors are carried out taking into account the rules defined for the exchange of products or services in agreed temporal horizons”. In this framework, several studies have explored LEM applications for prosumer integration. For instance, [11] presents a LEM designed to manage energy in a Spanish EC, while [12] develops a model allowing prosumers to act as buyers or sellers based on their consumption and self-generation. Similarly, [13] compares different LEM models using economic, market complexity, and congestion-related metrics.

Beyond energy trading, LEMs have been extended to include flexibility services. For example, [14] proposes a market design using ADMM for inter-DSO LEMs, enabling DSOs to trade flexibility under the coordination of a Local Market

Submitted to the 24th Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC 2026).

Operator (LMO). Several authors include flexibility services, accompanying the energy services already considered by the LEMs, such as [15] or [16], that proposed an LEM model to balance the generation and consumption using the flexibility from free capacity of users' batteries. That extends the concept of LEMs to Local Flexibility Markets (LFM), that, by analogy with the definitions of a local market, can be defined as a trading platform to trade flexibility in geographically limited areas such as communities or towns [17]. Thus, a LEM focuses on trading locally produced and consumed energy, while a LFM extends this concept to include flexibility services for grid support.

The design of local energy trading markets must account for both technical and economic considerations. Most studies on local energy trading in distribution networks primarily focus on economic objectives, such as increasing welfare or reducing costs. However, network constraints cannot be overlooked, as market participants rely on the physical infrastructure for energy exchanges [18]. For example, [19] examines structural elements and coordination schemes of local interaction models, analyzing the interaction between centrally operated LEMs and the wholesale market (WSM), but without incorporating network limitations. Similarly, [20] aims to reduce average energy costs by shifting demand to periods of high renewable availability or storing energy for later use, using an Agent-Based Model (ABM) with Q-Learning to simulate LEM interactions with the WSM, again without explicitly considering network constraints. Other works, including [21], [22], [23], also omit network constraints in their market formulations, although some allow the DSO to reject contracts that would violate limits, thereby preventing operational issues.

Different approaches have been proposed to integrate network constraints into local market models. Some studies, such as [24], [22], [25], include approximations of DC branch flow equations, while others, like [26], [27], consider full AC branch flow models. Alternatively, network limitations can be incorporated indirectly through financial or signaling mechanisms. For instance, [28] and [29] apply spatially and temporally varying network fees, and [30] uses a grid simulation to generate price signals that reflect network conditions, effectively creating a quasi-dynamic representation of power flows. These approaches illustrate the range of strategies for ensuring that local energy trading aligns with the technical realities of distribution networks.

Another critical aspect for maintaining the stability and resilience of the current network (without requiring costly upgrades) is effective congestion management, which aims to prevent overloading system components by reducing peak loads and avoiding potential failures [31]. However, if LEMs or LFMs are not properly designed or coordinated with grid constraints, they can produce negative effects on the network. Poorly structured market mechanisms may worsen congestion, trigger voltage instabilities, or increase operational stress on distribution assets. Few studies have directly examined the impacts of LEMs on power system operation, such as congestion, suggesting that while these markets are generally seen as

beneficial, the extent and nature of potential adverse effects remain underexplored in the literature [32].

For instance, [33] investigates the flexibility potential of residential heat pumps within LEMs using a double-sided auction framework, incorporating detailed models of energy devices, control strategies, and forecast errors. Despite this, no measures are included to manage the congestion that may result from these flexible actions. Similarly, [11] presents a two-stage centralized approach for managing a Local Energy Market aimed at prosumer integration, with energy planning in the first stage and real-time management in the second, yet it does not consider the potential congestion impacts on the distribution network infrastructure. These examples highlight the need for integrating congestion-aware mechanisms into LEM and LFM designs to ensure network reliability alongside market efficiency.

II. COORDINATION SCHEMES BETWEEN LEM/LFM END-USERS

The aim of this work is to build a mathematical model of a LFM that fills the gaps identified in the literature. After that, a study is conducted to assess how a developed LFM behaves with a forecasted load increase in the next years, and compare it to a case where users act independently outside an EC (then, they do not care about incurring in network violations and only prioritize their benefits).

To do so, we create two case-studies and simulate the results using the previous explained mathematical models, each time increasing the total household loads by a linear factor.

IND (Independent users case): Each user has its own optimal dispatch, that does not take into account network violations. The formulations from [34] are used to model this case.

LFM (Local Flexibility Market case): Users form a LFM that mitigate network violations. The LFM includes energy flexibility and can bid into a reserve market. The model presented in this work is used for this case.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Systematic comparison of coordination schemes within LEMs: To the best of our knowledge, no existing study provides a systematic comparison of different user coordination approaches within LEMs, nor analyzes how these strategies influence the network congestion. This work fills that gap.
- 2) Analysis of two representative coordination schemes: The first case considers independent users. Although EU is pushing forward to the adoption on LEMs, the current stage of LEM development is that most participants still act autonomously and market adoption remains limited. This case serves as a baseline for comparison with a LFM framework.
- 3) Integration of a stochastic formulation: While multi-stage formulations are common in the literature, only a

limited number explicitly incorporate uncertainty. This work introduces demand uncertainty into a two-stage stochastic optimization framework, where first-stage decisions define flexibility offers and second-stage operations respond to actual demand realizations.

- 4) Inclusion of network constraints in LEM operation: Few existing models explicitly account for the physical limits of the distribution network. In this study, network constraints are integrated into the market-clearing process.
- 5) Application of congestion management strategies: The proposed framework incorporates congestion management mechanisms within the LFM to ensure that the market operates efficiently and the grid operates reliably.

III. STOCHASTIC MODEL

The proposed model builds upon the formulation presented in [34], which described three separate optimization frameworks representing different stages in the energy dispatch process. A first model is used to specify the optimal energy dispatch of each user (minimizing costs), while the second examines whether the desired dispatch violates any network limitation. Then, in case of any violation, the third model tries to solve them by rescheduling some operations and allowing for P2P trading among users. In this work, these three models have been integrated into a unified framework capable of capturing the interactions between local generation, storage, and energy exchanges.

Beyond the structural integration, several methodological extensions have been introduced. First, demand uncertainty has been incorporated into the model, allowing for a more realistic representation. To handle this uncertainty, a two-stage stochastic optimization approach is proposed, and the continuous random variable representing demand uncertainty is discretized through a scenario-based formulation, which captures a representative set of possible realizations and their associated probabilities. Building on this stochastic framework, a local flexibility market is introduced in which reserve offers are submitted prior to the actual demand realization. To represent this mechanism, additional constraints are included to determine the amount of energy that can be offered in the reserve market according to the available flexibility of distributed resources. With all this explained, we present and explain the proposed model below.

The objective function (1a) aims to maximize the profit from the first-stage decisions (energy reserved $\zeta_{i,t}^u$ and $\zeta_{i,t}^d$ at price $\lambda_{i,t}^r$), plus the expected profit in (1c) (considering second stage variables for all scenarios) from the second stage (difference between energy sold $p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ at price λ_t^{sg} and bought $p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg}$ at price λ_t^{bg}), averaged across all scenarios by π_s , the probability of each.

$$\min \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} -\lambda_{i,t}^r (\zeta_{i,t}^{u,pv} + \zeta_{i,t}^{u,bt} + \zeta_{i,t}^{d,bt}) + \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad (1a)$$

subject to: *First stage constraints*

$$\text{where } \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) = E(\mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\xi})) = \quad (1b)$$

$$= \min \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \pi_s \left(\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \lambda_t^{bg} p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \lambda_t^{sg} p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{sg} \right) \quad (1c)$$

subject to: *Second stage constraints*

Since there are no first stage constraints, the following section will present the second stage. First, we will refer to the constraints related to DERs, which now include the possibility of reserving energy. For the solar panels, we have (2), where part of their capacity is reserved to offer more energy if the DSO wants to have it available ($\zeta_{i,t}^u$). Regarding the batteries, we have also included the possibility of reserving part of their capacity both to supply energy to the DSO ($\zeta_{i,t}^u$) and to absorb any excess energy ($\zeta_{i,t}^d$) that may exist. The SOC is computed in (3), but now it is needed to ensure space for the energy reserve in the battery, and this is done in both (4b) and (4c). However, we need to limit the SOC so that it does not surpass the capacity limits of the battery (4a).

$$pv_{i,t,s} + \zeta_{i,t}^{u,pv} \leq \Gamma_i^{pv} PV_{i,t}^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2)$$

$$soc_{i,t,s} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_i^{bt} + (\varphi^{ch} ch_{i,t,s} - \frac{1}{\varphi^{ds}} ds_{i,t,s}) \Delta t & \text{if } t = 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{S} \\ \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_i^{bt} & \text{if } t = 24 \\ soc_{i,t-1,s} + (\varphi^{ch} ch_{i,t,s} - \frac{1}{\varphi^{ds}} ds_{i,t,s}) \Delta t & \forall t/t \neq 0, i \in \mathcal{A}, s \in \mathcal{S} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\Gamma_i^{bt} SOC^{min} \leq soc_{i,t,s} \leq \Gamma_i^{bt} SOC^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4a)$$

$$\Gamma_i^{bt} SOC^{min} \leq soc_{i,t,s} - \zeta_{i,t}^{u,bt} \Delta t \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4b)$$

$$soc_{i,t,s} + \zeta_{i,t}^{d,bt} \Delta t \leq \Gamma_i^{bt} SOC^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4c)$$

Continuing with batteries, (5) prevents the SOC from surpassing the lower limit when discharging, and (6) and (7) impede charging and discharging at the same time. Moreover, these equations also consider that reserving battery limits the amount of power a user can charge or discharge in a given time.

$$SOC^{min} \Gamma_i^{bt} \leq soc_{i,t,s} - (ds_{i,t,s} + \zeta_{i,t}^{u,bt}) \Delta t \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5)$$

$$ch_{i,t,s} + \zeta_{i,t}^{d,bt} \leq PB^{bt} (1 - w_{i,t,s}) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (6)$$

$$ds_{i,t,s} + \zeta_{i,t}^{u,bt} \leq PB^{bt} w_{i,t,s} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, (8) manages the uncontrollable load of each bus taking into account the uncertain (but discretized in scenarios) variable (in our case, PL), while (9) and (10) ensure active and reactive power balance at buses.

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s} = pv_{i,t} - PL_{i,t,s} + ds_{i,t} - ch_{i,t} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j:(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} p_t^{i,j,s} - \sum_{j:(j,i) \in \mathcal{L}} (p_t^{j,i,s} - R_{j,i} l_t^{j,i,s}) = \\ & = \begin{cases} \Delta p_{i,t,s}, & \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \\ p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg} - p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{sg}, & \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \setminus \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j:(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} q_t^{i,j,s} - \sum_{j:(j,i) \in \mathcal{L}} (q_t^{j,i,s} - X_{j,i} l_t^{j,i,s}) qg_{i,t,s} - QL_{i,t,s} \\ & \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Additionally, (11) ensures the correct behavior of voltage in each line, while (12) aims to satisfy that the power flow stays within the line's capacity, and (13) limits it more to stay below a security level $SF_{i,j}$.

$$\begin{aligned} v_{j,t,s} = v_{i,t,s} - 2(R_{i,j} p_t^{i,j,s} + X_{i,j} q_t^{i,j,s}) + (R_{i,j}^2 + X_{i,j}^2) l_t^{j,i,s} \\ \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$(p_t^{i,j,s})^2 + (q_t^{i,j,s})^2 \leq l_t^{j,i,s} v_{i,t,s} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (12)$$

$$(p_t^{i,j,s})^2 + (q_t^{i,j,s})^2 \leq (S_{i,j}^{max} SF_{i,j})^2 \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (13)$$

Then, (14)-(17) introduce boundaries for voltage and power sold and bought from the main grid.

$$(V_i^{min})^2 \leq v_{i,t,s} \leq (V_i^{max})^2 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (14)$$

$$0 \leq p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg} \leq PBG_i^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (15)$$

$$0 \leq p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{sg} \leq PSG_i^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (16)$$

$$Q_i^{min} \leq qg_{i,t,s} \leq Q_i^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (17)$$

Regarding the imbalance of power at a bus, (18), (19) and (20) help classifying it into surplus or deficit. For their part, the surplus can be sold to the community or to the grid (21),

as well as the deficit can be supplied from the same sources (22).

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s} = \Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ - \Delta p_{i,t,s}^- \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ \leq My_{i,t,s} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^- \leq M(1 - y_{i,t,s}) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ = p_{i,t,s}^{sg} + p_{i,t,s}^{sm} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^- = p_{i,t,s}^{bg} + p_{i,t,s}^{bm} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (22)$$

Then, (23), (24) and (25) model the correct trade of energy between the grid or the users.

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{sg} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}} p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{sg} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{bg} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}} p\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{sm} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{bm} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (25)$$

And finally, (26)-(30) impose the domain of the variables.

$$\begin{aligned} & pv_{i,t,s}, ds_{i,t,s}, ch_{i,t,s}, soc_{i,t,s}, p_{i,t,s}^{bg}, p_{i,t,s}^{sg}, p_{i,t,s}^{bm}, p_{i,t,s}^{sm}, \\ & \Delta p_{i,t,s}^+, \Delta p_{i,t,s}^- \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}, \zeta_{i,t}^u, \zeta_{i,t}^d \in \mathbb{R} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (27)$$

$$p_{i,j,t,s}, q_{i,j,t,s}, l_t^{i,j,s} \in \mathbb{R} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (28)$$

$$v_{i,t,s}, qg_{i,t,s} \in \mathbb{R} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (29)$$

$$y_{i,t,s}, w_{i,t,s}, r_{i,t} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (30)$$

	PV		BESS	
	Nominal pow. (kW)	Capacity (kWh)	Capacity (kWh)	Pow. (kW)
# Units	31		16	
Total	195 kW	107.8 kWh	107.8 kWh	54.4 kW
# Type 1 Units	14 (5 kW/unit)	8 (5.5 kWh/unit)	8 (5.5 kWh/unit)	8 (3.4 kW/unit)
# Type 2 Units	11 (7 kW/unit)	6 (7.7 kWh/unit)	6 (7.7 kWh/unit)	6 (3.4 kW/unit)
# Type 3 Units	6 (8 kW/unit)	2 (8.8 kWh/unit)	2 (8.8 kWh/unit)	2 (3.4 kW/unit)

TABLE I
DER CHARACTERISTICS

Fig. 1. Representation of the LV network used in the study

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Data

The data used in this work are based on an equivalent network derived from the IEEE Low-Voltage Test Feeder [35], representing a residential 149-node system with DERs such as PV units and battery energy storage systems (BESS) installed at selected nodes, as illustrated in Figure 1. The network consists of two main branches converging toward the aggregator, with 55 nodes containing loads, while node 1 serves as the connection point between the energy community and the main distribution grid managed by the DSO. Load profiles (Figure 2) were obtained from [36], normalized to match the reported peak demand, and correspond to a typical weekday in August, showing the characteristic pattern of residential consumption (high during midday and lower in the evening). Regarding DER deployment, summarized in Table I, the system includes 31 PV installations totaling 195 kW of nominal capacity and 16 batteries providing 107.8 kWh of storage and 54.4 kW of discharge power. Finally, prices for the selected day are displayed in Figure 3.

B. Results

This section presents a comparative assessment on how different case studies behave under normal conditions and when an increase in demand is experienced. In Table II, the total cost (in €) for importing and exporting energy incurred

	Base	10%	20%	30% (max)
IND (€)	426.1	488.3	551.1	614.3
LFM (€)	353.67	410.5	467.66	527.39
Flex. benefit	-40.85	-40.04	-39.07	-35.96
Decrease (%)	17.00%	15.93%	15.14%	14.15%

TABLE II

OBJECTIVE VALUE DEPENDING ON THE INCREMENT OF LOAD.

Fig. 2. Network users' load profiles (kW).

Fig. 3. Electricity prices for the selected day in the study (€/MWh)

Fig. 4. Stacked results for the production and consumption (up) and energy trades (down) of agents for the base load in the two case-studies.

Fig. 5. Stacked results for the production and consumption (up) and energy trades (down) of agents for a 30% load increase in the two case-studies.

Fig. 6. Congestion heatmaps for IND (up) and LFM (for the most probable scenario) (down) cases in a 10% load increase.

by the aggregation of users¹ is exposed, depending on the increase in demand each case has undergone (designated in the first row). The outcomes for the LFM case include also the benefit they could get by offering flexibility bids to the DSO.

Focusing on the energy costs, forming an aggregated community that shares energy and is actively avoiding network violations results in a remarkable decrease in the total cost, especially for lower increases of load. This is due mainly to the reduced import of power and better utilization of renewables generated in the community. Moreover, red entries in Table II mean that the optimal dispatch for that case violates network limitations (i.e., the second model in [34] is unfeasible). In comparison, the LFM scheme is proven to handle a 30% load increase without any additional distribution infrastructure required. The aggregated results of these dispatches can be seen in Figures 4 and 5.

In each figure, the upper panel presents the aggregated production results (PV generation and battery discharging) alongside consumption results (battery charging and household demand). The lower panel displays the optimal energy exchange dispatch, including buying, selling, and sharing activities. At first glance, higher demand levels lead to a greater share of solar energy being used to meet consumption, leaving less surplus available for battery charging. The variations in charging and discharging patterns in both cases stem from congestion management actions. Demand growth also influences energy imports. For instance, at $t = 20$, under the base demand level, the LFM case imports more energy than the IND case; however, when demand increases, the LFM import remains stable while IND surpasses it. Energy is purchased at that time because afternoon prices are lower, thus minimizing total costs. This behavior, however, causes network limits to be exceeded at that instant. Consequently, the LFM case purchases less at $t = 20$, instead meeting demand through battery discharge and shifting imports to other periods, even at higher prices.

Figure 6 illustrates the congestion levels of the lines closest to the aggregator over time. In the IND case, the highest congestion occurs around $t = 20$, and these limits would be exceeded under higher demand. Conversely, in the LFM case, congestion reaches but does not exceed the limit. The model shifts certain actions to other time steps (e.g., congestion increases at $t = 22$ but decreases at $t = 16$). Therefore, incorporating a LFM model that reflects realistic conditions (by accounting for uncertainty) enables more efficient use of the network. It distributes power flows to prevent any line from exceeding 100% of its capacity, avoiding both under-utilization and overload events observed in the IND case.

During periods of high solar irradiance, batteries store excess PV generation by charging, later discharging once solar production decreases. This operation allows for a smoother balance between local generation and consumption throughout

¹Note that we refer to aggregation to encompass both case-studies: Aggregated results from all individual end-users, and aggregated community forming a LFM.

the day. As demand increases, battery utilization becomes more intensive, with higher discharge levels observed to meet as much of the local load as possible. Consequently, the system relies more heavily on stored energy to maintain supply adequacy during non-solar hours. At higher demand levels, this intensified use results in batteries being nearly depleted by the end of the day. In such conditions, users are primarily able to offer downward reserve bids, as storage units lack sufficient energy to increase their output further. In contrast, under base demand conditions, batteries retain a moderate state of charge, making upward reserve offers more feasible. Upward reserves are typically provided when batteries begin to charge (indicating available capacity to reduce consumption if required) while downward reserves are offered when the batteries are not yet full and could absorb additional energy.

It is important to note that reserve provision is modeled only as reservation of energy and is not activated during operation. As a result, the profits obtained from participating in the flexibility market represent an upper bound of the potential economic benefits rather than the realized gains. This approach allows assessing the theoretical value of flexibility under ideal conditions, where all reserve offers could be fully remunerated without activation or opportunity costs associated with real-time operation.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate that the case study operating without consideration of network constraints is more prone to congestion problems, especially as demand levels rise. In contrast, when congestion-aware coordination mechanisms are implemented, the network's ability to adapt to growing demand improves significantly. This improvement is mainly achieved through the strategic operation of BESS and P2P energy sharing, which together enable a more balanced and flexible distribution of power flows across the grid.

Moreover, incorporating participation in a local reserve (flexibility) market through a stochastic modeling framework enhances the realism and adaptability of energy planning within ECs. By accounting for demand uncertainty, the proposed approach enables more effective use of available flexibility, extending the network's operational capability and delaying the need for costly grid reinforcements. This combination of stochastic reserve participation and P2P trading not only contributes to congestion relief but also results in overall cost reductions for community members, highlighting the potential of well-coordinated and market-integrated ECs to support both economic efficiency and grid reliability.

However, it is important to emphasize that this work constitutes an initial step toward a more complete modeling of flexibility services within LEMs. The current formulation focuses on the theoretical design of the reserve market and quantifies its potential economic benefits under idealized conditions. Since the activation of flexibility bids is not modeled, the resulting benefits represent an upper bound of the real gains that could be achieved in practice. Future developments will aim to extend the framework by considering different

TABLE III
NOMENCLATURE

Sets	
\mathcal{B}	Set of buses.
\mathcal{T}	Set of time periods.
\mathcal{S}	Set of scenarios.
\mathcal{A}	Set of agents/users that share energy in the local market, $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathcal{B}$.
\mathcal{L}	Set of lines, $\mathcal{L} = \{(i, j); i, j \in \mathcal{B}\}$.

TABLE IV
PARAMETERS

$PL_{i,t}$	Active power load of bus i at period t [kW].
$QL_{i,t}$	Reactive power load of bus i at period t [kW].
$PV_{i,t}^{\max}$	Maximum PV energy that can be generated at bus i during period t (normalized between 0 and 1).
Γ_i^{pv}	Installed nominal power of PV generation at bus i [kW].
Γ_i^{bt}	Installed capacity of battery i [kWh].
$\varphi^{ch/ds}$	Charging/discharging efficiency of batteries (between 0 and 1).
PB^{bt}	Battery power rate [kW].
$SOC^{\min/\max}$	Minimum/maximum state of charge for battery i at period t [kWh].
$X_{i,j}$	Reactance between buses i and j [p.u.].
$R_{i,j}$	Resistance between buses i and j [p.u.].
$V_i^{\min/\max}$	Minimum/maximum voltage allowed at bus i [p.u.].
$Q_i^{\min/\max}$	Lower/upper limit for reactive power imported at bus i [p.u.].
$S_{i,j}^{\max}$	Power flow limit in line (i, j) [kW].
$SF_{i,j}$	Security factor for power flow on line (i, j) .
$\lambda_t^{bg/sg}$	Purchase/selling price of electricity from/to the grid at time t [€/MW].
λ_t^r	Energy reserve reward at time t [€/MW].
PSG_i^{\max}	Maximum power that bus i can sell to the grid [kW].
PBG_i^{\max}	Maximum power that bus i can buy from the grid [kW].

grid topologies, thereby providing more robust conclusions on how network structure influences congestion patterns and the effectiveness of flexibility mechanisms. Additionally, alternative methods will be studied for distributing the economic and operational benefits among participants, ensuring fair and efficient outcomes that enhance engagement within the LEMs.

VI. NOMENCLATURE

A summary for the notation used in the work is in Tables III, IV and V.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the assistance of the TED2021-131365B-C41, PID2021-128574OB-I00 and RYC2021-033477-I grants, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union "NextGenerationEU"/PRTR.

REFERENCES

- [1] Council of European Union, "Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources," 2018. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/2001/oj/eng>.

TABLE V
VARIABLES

$pv_{i,t}$	Active power generated by the PV system at bus i and period t [kW].
$soc_{i,t}$	State of charge of battery i at period t [kWh].
$ch_{i,t}$	Power charged to the battery at bus i and period t [kW].
$ds_{i,t}$	Power discharged from the battery at bus i and period t [kW].
$w_{i,t}$	Binary variable: 1 if the battery at bus i discharges at period t , 0 otherwise.
$\Delta p_{i,t}$	Difference between self-generated energy and consumption at bus i and period t [kW].
$\Delta p_{i,t}^{+/-}$	Power surplus/deficit at bus i and period t [kW].
$y_{i,t}$	Binary variable: 1 if agent i has an energy surplus at period t , 0 otherwise.
$p_t^{i,j}$	Active power flow in the line between buses i and j at period t [kW].
$q_t^{i,j}$	Reactive power flow in the line between buses i and j at period t [kVar].
$v_{i,t}$	Voltage magnitude at bus i and period t [p.u.].
$\bar{l}_t^{i,j}$	Complex current magnitude from bus i to j [kVA].
$p_{i,t}^{bg/sg}$	Power bought from/sold to the grid by user i at period t [kW].
$p_{i,t}^{sm/bm}$	Power given to/received from the local market by user i at period t [kW].
$p\kappa_{i,t}^{bg/sg}$	Active power bought from/sold to the grid by buses i at period t [kW].
$qg_{i,t}$	Reactive power imported from the grid by bus i at period t [kVar].
$\zeta_{i,t}^{u/d,bt/pv}$	Upward/downward reserve power from the battery or PV at bus i and time t [kW].

[2] Council of European Union, "Stepping up europe's 2030 climate ambition investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people," 2020.
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52020DC0562>.

[3] Council of European Union, "Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652," 2023.
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32023L2413>.

[4] P. Johansson, M. Vendel, and C. Nuur, "Integrating distributed energy resources in electricity distribution systems: An explorative study of challenges facing dsos in sweden," *Utilities Policy*, vol. 67, p. 101117, 2020.

[5] International Energy Agency, "Global Energy Review 2025," 2025.
<https://www.iea.org/reports/global-energy-review-2025>.

[6] V. Dudjak, D. Neves, T. Alskaif, S. Khadem, A. Pena-Bello, P. Saggese, B. Bowler, M. Andoni, M. Bertolini, Y. Zhou, *et al.*, "Impact of local energy markets integration in power systems layer: A comprehensive review," *Applied Energy*, vol. 301, p. 117434, 2021.

[7] R. Faia, F. Lezama, J. Soares, T. Pinto, and Z. Vale, "Local electricity markets: A review on benefits, barriers, current trends and future perspectives," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 190, p. 114006, 2024.

[8] A. Lüth, J. M. Zepter, P. Crespo del Granado, and R. Egging, "Local electricity market designs for peer-to-peer trading: The role of battery flexibility," *Applied Energy*, vol. 229, pp. 1233–1243, 2018.

[9] F. Teotia and R. Bhakar, "Local energy markets: Concept, design and operation," in *2016 National Power Systems Conference (NPSC)*, pp. 1–6, 2016.

[10] E. Mengelkamp, J. Gärtner, K. Rock, S. Kessler, L. Orsini, and C. Weinhardt, "Designing microgrid energy markets: A case study: The brooklyn microgrid," *Applied Energy*, vol. 210, pp. 870–880, 2018.

[11] N. Goitia-Zabaleta, A. Milo, H. Gaztanaga, and E. Fernandez, "Two-stage centralised management of local energy market for prosumers

integration in a community-based p2p," *Applied Energy*, vol. 348, p. 121552, 2023.

[12] F. Garcia-Muñoz, S. Dávila, and F. Quezada, "A benders decomposition approach for solving a two-stage local energy market problem under uncertainty," *Applied Energy*, vol. 329, p. 120226, 2023.

[13] M. Galici, M. Troncia, M. Nour, J. P. Chaves-Ávila, and F. Pilo, "Comparative techno-economic analysis of market models for peer-to-peer energy trading on a distributed platform," *Applied Energy*, vol. 380, p. 125005, 2025.

[14] J. A. Aguado and Á. Paredes, "Coordinated and decentralized trading of flexibility products in inter-dso local electricity markets via admm," *Applied Energy*, vol. 337, p. 120893, 2023.

[15] A. Esmat, J. Usaola, and M. Á. Moreno, "Distribution-level flexibility market for congestion management," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 1056, 2018.

[16] A. Lüth, J. M. Zepter, P. C. Del Granado, and R. Egging, "Local electricity market designs for peer-to-peer trading: The role of battery flexibility," *Applied Energy*, vol. 229, pp. 1233–1243, 2018.

[17] X. Jin, Q. Wu, and H. Jia, "Local flexibility markets: Literature review on concepts, models and clearing methods," *Applied Energy*, vol. 261, p. 114387, 2020.

[18] M. Khorasany, Y. Mishra, and G. Ledwich, "Market framework for local energy trading: A review of potential designs and market clearing approaches," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 12, no. 22, pp. 5899–5908, 2018.

[19] N. Chrysanthopoulos, Y. Y. Chan, and G. Strbac, "Local energy markets: Structural elements and the effects of upscaling," in *2024 20th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2024.

[20] A. F. dos Santos and J. T. Saraiva, "An agent based model applied to a local energy market (lem) considering demand response (dr) and its interaction with the wholesale market (wsm)," in *2024 20th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2024.

[21] Y. Okawa and T. Namerikawa, "Distributed optimal power management via negawatt trading in real-time electricity market," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3009–3019, 2017.

[22] J. Qin, R. Rajagopal, and P. Varaiya, "Flexible market for smart grid: Coordinated trading of contingent contracts," *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1657–1667, 2017.

[23] Y. Liu, L. Wu, and J. Li, "Peer-to-peer (p2p) electricity trading in distribution systems of the future," *The Electricity Journal*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 2–6, 2019.

[24] S. Wang, A. F. Taha, J. Wang, K. Kvaternik, and A. Hahn, "Energy crowdsourcing and peer-to-peer energy trading in blockchain-enabled smart grids," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 49, no. 8, pp. 1612–1623, 2019.

[25] A. Masood, J. Hu, A. Xin, A. R. Sayed, and G. Yang, "Transactive energy for aggregated electric vehicles to reduce system peak load considering network constraints," *Ieee Access*, vol. 8, pp. 31519–31529, 2020.

[26] T. AlSkaif and G. Van Leeuwen, "Decentralized optimal power flow in distribution networks using blockchain," in *2019 International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies (SEST)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2019.

[27] G. Van Leeuwen, T. AlSkaif, M. Gibescu, and W. Van Sark, "An integrated blockchain-based energy management platform with bilateral trading for microgrid communities," *Applied Energy*, vol. 263, p. 114613, 2020.

[28] F. Moret and P. Pinson, "Energy collectives: A community and fairness based approach to future electricity markets," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 3994–4004, 2018.

[29] T. Baroche, P. Pinson, R. L. G. Latimier, and H. B. Ahmed, "Exogenous cost allocation in peer-to-peer electricity markets," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 2553–2564, 2019.

[30] T. Almomani, S. Englberger, A. Jossen, and R. Witzmann, "Aggregating residential energy storages and electric vehicles through peer-to-peer local energy markets in low voltage distribution grids," in *NEIS 2021; Conference on Sustainable Energy Supply and Energy Storage Systems*, pp. 1–6, VDE, 2021.

[31] H. de Heer, M. van der Laan, A. Sáez-Armenteros, "Usef: The framework explained," 2021.
<https://www.usef.energy/news-events/publications/>.

- [32] M. Mohiti, M. Mazidi, D. Steen, and L. A. Tuan, "A decentralized local flexibility market for local energy communities to mitigate grid congestion: A case study in sweden," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.20697*, 2025.
- [33] Z. You, S. D. Lumpp, M. Doepfert, P. Tzscheutschler, and C. Goebel, "Leveraging flexibility of residential heat pumps through local energy markets," *Applied Energy*, vol. 355, p. 122269, 2024.
- [34] F. García-Muñoz, S. San Martín, and J. Eichman, "Empowering energy communities by a user-centric model for self-managed congestion via local p2p and flexibility markets," in *2024 20th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2024.
- [35] M. A. Khan and B. Hayes, "For paper "a reduced electrically-equivalent model of the ieee european low voltage test feeder"," 2020.
- [36] OpenEI, "Commercial and residential load data," 2004. <https://data.openei.org/submissions/153>.